

1 **Epithelial mesenchymal transition modulation during resistance to chemotherapy in human TNBC.**

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7 We report here modulation of the epithelial mesenchymal transition (EMT) program during resistance to
8 chemotherapy in human TNBC. Nuclear effectors important for EMT program were activated, including
9 *SNAI1*. Evidence of program engagement observed was activation of collagens *COL1A1* and *COL6A3*.
10 Evidence of matrix milieu changes included activation of MMPs *MMP2* and *MMP17* with silencing of
11 *MMP14*.

12 Citations

13 1. English, W.R., Puente, X.S., Freije, J.M., Knäuper, V., Amour, A., Merryweather, A., López-Otín, C.
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15 convertase activity but does not activate pro-MMP2. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 275(19),
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